

SUBTYPES ISOLATION FROM PATIENTS WITH *ENTAMOEBAS* SP. INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

Amebiasis is most diffusion in area with lowest levels of cleanliness, deal with animal and inappropriate elimination system. The goal of this research is subtype *Entamoeba* sp., isolate from diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients used by sequence 18S ribosomal DNA. Taken 200 stool samples are collecting of diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients from Euphrates Hospital in Al-Najaf province during January to July 2022. Concentrated for all samples were by used traditional Formalin- ether technique and examined by the light microscopic. As process stool samples by cultivation in the clotted foetal goat milieu where examination for grow of Amebiasis each 48h with direct smear slide for 10 days. Performed of DNA extraction to whole positive samples, DNA amplification fragments the 18S rDNA is sequence and comparison with indication gene already deposition in the Genbank database. Numbers the diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients of this research was 75 (26.18%) and 125 (23.72%), respectively. Selected three subtypes specific of the positive samples, *E. dispar* (ST2) was most prevailing (38.5%) followed by *E. histolytica* (ST1) (35.4%) and *E. moshkovskii* (ST3) was (31.2%) as showed no mixed subtypes. Almost prevalent subtypes in diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients were *E. dispar* (ST2) was (38.71%) and *E. histolytica* (ST1) was (36.84%) respectively. The conclusion of *Entamoeba* sp., is more prevalent among diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients. Actually, *E. dispar* (ST2) was mostly prevalent especially in the samples collected from diarrheal patients.

Keywords: *Entamoeba* sp., Subtypes, 18S rDNA, Al-Najaf.

INTRODUCTION:

Entamoeba sp., is shelter in the humans gastrointestinal tract has various grades of pathogenic on the audience health [1]. Even thought that *E. histolytica*, *E. dispar* and *E. moshkovskii* were morphological similar but pathogenicity the *E. dispar* and *E. moshkovskii* are remains vague [2]. Believe some researchers that the species affiliated with this parasite involvement in the manner of development of disease, while appeared danger of the infection act on elevate the symptoms [3]. Familiarly, detection in the laboratory of *Entamoeba* sp., of human feces by microscopic examination in the feces samples, but cannot this method distinguishes of pathogenicity of *E. histolytica*, coexistence *E. dispar* and widespread *E. moshkovskii* [4]. Molecular realization reveals that prevalent *E. dispar* was higher ten times than *E. histolytica* of worldwide [5] Almost molecular researches of *Entamoeba* sp., has using by PCR assays for detection of *E. histolytica* and *E. dispar* whereas detect of *E. moshkovskii* was underestimation [4] In studied described of molecular allocation of *Entamoeba* subtypes executed in different area by used PCR-RFLP and sequences tagging size primer subtypes [6]. Primers chosen, the number and site of the

mutation and mixing subtypes are limitations of RFLP path [7]. A subtype's primers were lesser sensitivity compared with amplified 18S rDNA for *Amoebiasis* [8]. The current study of estimated frequency and subtypes allocation of *Amoebiasis* sp., by using amplified of SSU rDNA in diarrheal and non-diarrheal in the patients [2]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples preparation: Collected of diarrheic and non-diarrheic patients were 200 stool samples from Euphrates Hospital in Al-Najaf province, from January to July 2022. Freshly samples were transmitted to laboratory of the same hospital then divided into two parts, first part for microscopically examination and other parts for cultivation. These samples were planned used traditional formalin-ether technicality and examined by the light microscopic. This study was confirmed by Ethics Committee of Kufa University, as taken from patients pre-approval.

Culture of samples: Cultivated the wet stool samples in liquid medium with some amendments [9]. By autoclave where added 2ml Locke's solution to 4ml sloping clotted foetal goat serum to the tube, added 100mg from feces samples with 4mg /ml streptomycin to every cultivated tube then incubated the samples at 37 °C in anaerobic conditions duration ten days. Examined whole cultured for growth of *Amebiasis* for 48hr then examined by direct smear slides for ten days. After ten days in this cultures if the parasite was not seen was reported negative samples.

Extraction of DNA and Subtyping: Transferred 300 µl of the liquid stage from the medium of positive samples to 2 ml of tube then put in centrifuge for 5 min at 5000 rpm, the pellet inserted to i-genomic feces extraction of DNA (Dragons Teaching Limited, Hong Kong) kit. Storage the clarified DNA at -20°C until used.

Amplification of DNA was achievement on positive samples only by used 18S rDNA special primers, included F1 (5'-GGAGGTAGTGACAATAAATC-3') and BHCRseq3 (5'-TAAGACTACGAGGGTA TCTA-3') (Khairnar, 2007). The primers amplifier 550 bp segment of SSU rDNA of *Entamoeba* sp., depending on the protocol: at 95°C was denaturation duration 9 min, 45 cycle at 95 °C for 60 sec, 55 °C for 40 sec, 74 °C for 50 sec continued to end expansion. 15 µL for each PCR product were electrophoresis on 2% Agarose gel in TBE (0.09M Tris, 0.09M boric acid, 2mM EDTA) where staining with 0.7 µg /mL Ethidium bromide and visualization by used UV transilluminator [10].

Statistical analysis:

Data were analyses and processed by using Microsoft Excel software SPSS (version 12.0, Chicago, USA) program for analyses. The proportion percentage included recurrence *Entamoeba* sp., infection according to variables and subtype distribution among studied individuals. This result was compared with existent in the GenBank database.

RESULTS

Table 1. Frequency of *Entamoeba* sp., specific by traditional Formalin-ether and cultivate in diarrheal & non-diarrheal patients.

VARIABLES	FORMALIN-ETHER NO. (%)		CULTIVATE NO. (%)	
	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Diarrheal patients	25(14.21%)	50(38.16%)	30(22.8%)	45(31.2%)
Non-diarrheal patients	40(12.32%)	85(35.12%)	45(20.07%)	80(30.61%)
Total	65(13.3%)	135(36.6%)	75(21.4%)	125(30.9%)

70 (21.6%) and 130 (65.4%) taken from stool samples, *Entamoeba* sp. both female and male respectively. As showed that 65(13.3%) and 75(21.4%) samples from formalin-ether concentrations and culture, respectively. Number of diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients for these the study is 75 (26.18%) and 125 (23.72%), respectively as in Table 1.

Table 2. Frequencies subtypes of *Entamoeba* sp., secluded from diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients

VARIABLES	DIARRHEAL PATIENTS	NON-DIARRHEAL PATIENTS	TOTAL NO.(%)
<i>E.histolytica</i> (ST1)	9	14	23(35.4)
<i>E.dispar</i> (ST2)	12	13	25(38.5)
<i>E.moshkovskii</i> (ST3)	10	11	21(31.2)
Mixing Subtypes	none	None	none
Total	31	38	69

Edited Whole sequences and compared with sequences which are ready in GenBank database. Identified three subtypes from whole positive samples used PCR and sequences 18S rDNA. *E.dispar* (ST2) was more diffused (38.5%) then followed *E.histolytica* (ST1) (35.4%) and the *E.moshkovskii* (ST3) was (31.2%). While no mixing subtypes and more diffused subtypes in diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients were in *E.dispar* (ST2) was (38.71%) and *E.histolytica* (ST1) was (36.84%) respectively as in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

Entamoeba sp., considered as the most common parasites in the world, there are many reports from the human and animals [11] There are studied showed that *Entamoeba* sp., are similar in morphological but difference in the genetic and pathogenic [12]. Many studies showed high spread rate to this parasite distinguish *Entamoeba* sp., and to estimate spread of *E.dispa*, *E.histolytica* and *E.moshkovskii* in Iraq [13]. In present study, *Entamoeba* sp., observed in 21.4% samples cultivated in LE medium. An almost study has been complete used direct smear slide and iodine stain whilst

cultivated increases sensitivity of detecting. As agreement this study with [14]. that higher spread of *Amebiasis* in culture medium compared to the microscopic method [15]

As showed in current study that *E.histolytica* (ST1), *E.dispar* (ST2) and *E.moshkovskii* (ST3) were acquired from diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients. A study in Iran population showed that *E.moshkovskii* (ST3) was more popular subtypes then followed by *E.histolytica* (ST1)[16]. In Arab Emirates, *E.histolytica* (ST1) was predominantly subtyped, whilst *E.dispar* (ST2) and *E.moshkovskii* (ST3) were less spread [10]. In our study, *E.dispar* (ST2) was the predominantly following by *E.histolytica* (ST1) and *E.moshkovskii* (ST3). Depending (PCR-RFLP) approaching, *E.histolytica* (ST1) was great mutual subtype whilst in other research depends STS primers; *E.moshkovskii* (ST3) was prevailing subtype[17].

Another studies showed prevalence of *E.histolytica* (ST1) in symptomatic and inflammatory bowel syndrome in patients was more than another subtypes, so characterized as pathogens subtype[18]. Evident related between other subtypes and various clinical exhibitory, as noted in this study *E.dispar* (ST2) was predominant subtype in patients diarrhea, whilst *E.histolytica* (ST1) show less spread subtype to non-diarrheal patients. In other study of *E.histolytica* (ST1) was no reported of predominant subtype of patients whereas *E.histolytica* (ST1) significantly most spread in gastrointestinal patients[19]. Concluded from this study that *Entamoeba* sp., is more spread among diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients and *E.dispar* (ST2) was most common subtype in the positive samples specially.

Conclusion : *Entamoeba* sp., is more prevalent among diarrheal and non-diarrheal patients. Actually, *E.dispar* (ST2) was mostly prevalent especially in the samples collected from diarrheal patients.

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Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval: The study was approved by the Human Research .Ethics Committee of the University of Kufa (approval ID MEC/5.1.2022)

Consent to participate: Participants received written informed consent before participating in the study.

Authorship: HAS contributed to data collection. SAS contributed to writing the original draft, methodology, and editing, HAS contributed to conceptualizing the study. ZAS contributed to data analysis and data curation.

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